

Annex A (prompt applied to Gemini 2.5 Pro in March 2026 to identify specific contribution of scientific papers in policy documents found at Overton database)

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Prompt

You will analyze pairs (reference + context excerpt) taken from a public policy document.

Data structure:

- There is a list of bibliographic references and a list of context excerpts.
- In both lists, the items are in the SAME order.
- Within each list, the items are separated by the marker '|||'.
- Thus, the first item in the list of references corresponds to the first item in the list of context excerpts, the second to the second, and so on.

Your task:

- For EACH context excerpt, choose ONLY ONE category from:

a) "Supports the justification and/or rationale of the policy."

Use this when the excerpt uses the reference to justify or support the policy, describing the problem, risks, inequalities or the need for intervention. Even if there are data, the focus is on sustaining the argumentation and the legitimacy of the policy.

b) "Provides data and/or results used in the policy."

Use this when the excerpt presents data, numbers, percentages, indicators or empirical results (for example, rates, prevalences, time series, evaluation results) that are used to describe the magnitude of the problem, define targets, compare scenarios or monitor the policy. In case of doubt between (a) and (b), if there are specific numerical data, prioritize this category.

c) "Theoretical and/or conceptual nature."

Use this when the excerpt uses the reference to define concepts, categories, typologies, theoretical models or conceptual frameworks. The emphasis is on explaining how to understand the problem or the policy in theoretical or conceptual terms.

d) "Other nature (specify which)."

Use this when the reference is cited with another identifiable function that does not fit well in the previous categories, for example: mainly methodological purposes (instruments, techniques, scales, software) or complementary illustrations/historical notes. When you choose this category, you MUST replace the text "specify which" with a very short specification (1-4 English words) of this other nature, in parentheses.

For example:

- "Other nature (methodological)";
- "Other nature (historical comparison)";
- "Other nature (implementation details)";

Never output the literal string "Other nature (specify which)" in your answer.

- If the excerpt is only a table, an isolated number, an isolated bibliographic reference, or if it is not possible to understand the use of the evidence, classify it as "undetermined".

INPUT FORMAT:

- References (items separated by '|||', in order): {references}

- Context excerpts (items separated by "|||", in the same order): {contexts}

OUTPUT FORMAT (STRICT):

- Return ONLY a single line of text.
- This line must contain EXACTLY one label for each context excerpt, in the same order in which they appear in the list above.
- Use ONLY the following labels (copy them exactly), with a specific rule for "Other nature":
 - "Supports the justification and/or rationale of the policy";*
 - "Provides data and/or results used in the policy";*
 - "Theoretical and/or conceptual nature".*
 - A label that starts with "Other nature (" and ends with ")", where inside the parentheses you briefly specify the nature in 1-4 English words "undetermined".*
- Separate the labels with a semicolon followed by a space: ";".
- Do not include numbered labels, additional explanations, reference names, or any other text.

Example (for three excerpts):

"Supports the justification and/or rationale of the policy; Provides data and/or results used in the policy; Other nature (methodological)".

Now answer only with the single line of categories, in the specified format.

Annex B (prompt)

You are an expert in science–policy interfaces, research evaluation and qualitative content analysis.

Your task is to answer, in a scientific and well-grounded way, the central question: "What is the contribution of the cited scientific article to the policy document that cites it?"

To do so, you must use three sources of information:

1. the article abstract;
2. the description of the policy document;
3. a previous classification of how the article was used in a specific policy excerpt (column "Contribution category").

You will receive:

- Cited article DOI: {doi};
- Article abstract: {article_abstract};
- Policy document ID: {policy_id};
- Policy document description: {policy_description};
- Previous classification of the use of the article in the cited policy excerpt (column "Contribution category"): {contribution_category}.

The "Contribution category" column may contain one or more categories, separated by semicolons (";").

This means that in some cases the same article is used in the policy with multiple simultaneous functions (for example, to justify the policy and at the same time to provide empirical data or a conceptual framework).

You must interpret all categories present in this column as complementary evidence about how the article is mobilized in the policy.

PART 1 – SYNTHETIC SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT OF CONTRIBUTION

Based on the combination of the abstract, the policy description and the categories in "Contribution category", write a concise yet scientifically grounded assessment that directly answers the question: "What is the substantive contribution of this article to the policy document?"

Guidelines:

- Write in English, between 3 and 6 sentences, with no bullet points.
- Focus on the ROLE of the article for the policy, not on simply repeating the abstract.

- Connect elements of the abstract (problem, methods, results, concepts) with elements of the policy description (goals, instruments, target population, governance, evaluation, institutional context, etc.).
- Use the information from the "Contribution category" column as additional evidence about how the article is actually mobilized in the cited excerpt: for example, whether it appears as justification, empirical evidence, conceptual/theoretical framework, methodological reference or another specific function.
- When there is more than one category separated by ";", assume that the article may perform more than one function at the same time and try to integrate this into your synthesis.
- If the available information is very weak (for example, abstract and description are missing or extremely short), explicitly state that the contribution cannot be inferred with confidence and briefly describe this limitation.

The text produced in this step will be used to fill a spreadsheet column called "Contribution Assessment" and will be stored in the field "contribution_assessment".

PART 2 – THEMATIC ADHERENCE TO SPECIFIC AXES

Now evaluate whether the article's contribution to the policy document is thematically related to ANY of the following axes (consider both explicit mentions and strong conceptual proximity): diversity; equity; inclusion; innovation policy; intellectual property; metascience; science advice; science diplomacy; science policy; technology offset; technology transfer; trust in science.

Instructions:

- 1) Consider the scientific article AND the way it is used in the policy document (based on the description and the categories in "Contribution category").
- 2) If at least ONE of the axes above is clearly relevant to the article's contribution to the policy, you MUST:
 - set "adherence_overall" = "YES", and;
 - list in "adherence_terms" ONLY the axes that are meaningfully related, using exactly the strings from the list above (for example: ["equity", "science policy"]).
- 3) If NONE of the axes has a substantive relation with the article's contribution, you MUST:
 - set "adherence_overall" = "NO", and;
 - set "adherence_terms" as an empty list: [].
- 4) In ALL cases, write a very concise explanation in English, with 2-4 sentences:
 - If "YES": briefly explain WHY and HOW the contribution connects to the axes you selected (for example, how it addresses equity, inclusion, science policy, technology transfer, metascience, trust in science, etc.).
 - If "NO": briefly explain why there is no substantive or explicit connection to those axes, indicating what seems to be the main thematic focus of the article and the policy instead (for example, a very specific technical problem, a clinical issue, or a management topic that does not directly relate to those axes).

This explanation will be stored in separate spreadsheet columns (together with "adherence_overall" and "adherence_terms") and will be stored in the field "adherence_explanation".

SPECIAL RULE FOR VERY LIMITED INFORMATION:

- If both the article abstract and the policy document description are missing or extremely short (for example, less than 20 words each), you MUST:
 - set "adherence_overall" = "NO",
 - set "adherence_terms" = [],
 - and in "adherence_explanation" state that the available information is insufficient to reliably assess thematic adherence.

OUTPUT FORMAT (STRICT)

Return ONLY ONE line of text.

This line must be a single valid JSON object with EXACTLY the following fields:

- "contribution_assessment": "<3-6 sentences in English, NO line breaks, directly answering: 'What is the contribution of this article to the policy document?'>",
- "adherence_overall": "<either 'YES' or 'NO'>",
- "adherence_terms": [<zero or more strings from the list of axes above>],
- "adherence_explanation": "<2-4 sentences in English, NO line breaks>".

Important:

- Do NOT include newline characters (\n) inside any field values.
- Do NOT repeat the DOI or the policy document ID in the JSON fields.
- Do NOT add any other fields.
- Do NOT add comments, labels or any text outside the JSON.
- Do NOT wrap the JSON in Markdown or backticks.

Now, based on the information provided, output ONLY the JSON object in a single line.